

THE DIDACTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF INCLUSIVE, DIFFERENTIATED, AND STEAM APPROACHES IN DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN A DUAL EDUCATION CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the didactic potential of inclusive education, differentiated instruction, and the STEAM approach in the development of professional competence of future primary school teachers within a dual education framework, from both theoretical and practical perspectives. Furthermore, the effectiveness of integrating theory and practice based on the “4+2” model is substantiated.

In the process of developing the professional competence of future primary school teachers within a dual education system, the implementation of inclusive education principles and the effective use of differentiated approaches have become particularly relevant among modern pedagogical requirements. This is due to the fact that in today's primary education system, students differ not only in age and individual characteristics but also in their needs, abilities, levels of achievement, health conditions, psychophysiological states, and social adaptation.

This situation requires teachers to be able to adapt the educational process, individualize learning content, and ensure equal opportunities for every learner. Therefore, in the training of future teachers under dual education conditions, inclusive education and differentiated instruction serve as essential didactic components in the development of professional competence.

The specificity of dual education lies in the fact that future primary school teachers engage in real school environments, where they directly observe various pedagogical situations that may arise in inclusive classrooms and attempt to find practical solutions during their teaching practice. In particular, the integrated learning process based on the “4+2” model effectively connects theoretical preparation with school practice, allowing students to test modern methodological approaches to inclusive education in real conditions [1].

Thus, mastering inclusive education and differentiated instruction contributes to the development of activity-based (practical) and communicative competencies, which are integral components of a teacher's professional competence.

Inclusive education is a socio-pedagogical system aimed at ensuring every child's right to education by organizing the learning process according to their needs and capabilities. The primary education stage is characterized by the socialization of the individual, the formation of basic learning skills, and the development of self-confidence. Therefore, in an inclusive environment, the teacher acts not only as a knowledge provider but also as a professional who supports individual development, ensures social adaptation, and creates a psychologically comfortable learning environment.

In a dual education context, the formation of inclusive competence in future primary school teachers requires solving the following didactic tasks: applying individualized approaches when working with students with diverse needs; mastering skills of adapting educational content; organizing assessment processes in a variable manner; using pedagogical communication methods that support the learner's personality; creating a collaborative learning environment. These tasks contribute to the comprehensive development of the teacher's professional competence.

The differentiated approach is one of the key didactic mechanisms that enhance the methodological effectiveness of the learning process in primary education, as it involves providing tasks that correspond to students' levels of achievement and individual needs. Within the dual education system, future teachers not only study this approach theoretically but also apply it in real classroom practice during their school placements.

In this process, students perform the following practical tasks: analyzing students according to their levels of achievement; adapting teaching methods for individual and group instruction; developing a bank of differentiated tasks; selecting effective motivational strategies for students; applying individualized approaches in criterion-based assessment.

Thus, the differentiated approach strengthens the methodological competence of future teachers and becomes an important tool for developing their activity-based professional competence.

In the context of dual education, the systematic application of the following didactic tools is considered appropriate for implementing an inclusive approach by future primary school teachers:

1) Bank of differentiated tasks. A bank of differentiated tasks enables the provision of assignments of varying levels of complexity according to students' levels of achievement. This tool allows future teachers to design tasks at "minimum–standard–maximum" levels during lessons and to coordinate the learning activities of students with diverse abilities.

2) Adapted learning materials. In an inclusive classroom, it is often necessary to simplify learning materials for certain students, enhance visual representation, and use supportive visual aids. Adapted materials (illustrated cards, diagrams, short-text tasks, audio materials) increase students' comprehension capacity and ensure the principle of equal opportunities in the learning process.

3) Individual Education Plans (IEPs). In a dual education setting, Individual Education Plans serve as an important methodological tool in developing the inclusive competence of future teachers. IEPs involve defining goals, tasks, methods, and assessment criteria tailored to the learner's needs. This, in turn, contributes to the development of the teacher's pedagogical diagnostic competence.

4) Visual and multisensory tools. The principle of visualization is crucial in primary education, and in inclusive classrooms it becomes an even stronger didactic factor. A multisensory approach (learning through visual, auditory, and kinesthetic perception) enhances learning effectiveness and requires teachers to select appropriate didactic tools.

5) Formative assessment tools. In inclusive education, assessment is not limited to determining final outcomes but includes formative assessment methods that encourage small achievements and reflect students' developmental dynamics. These include checklists, rubrics, and continuous monitoring. Such tools develop the reflective and diagnostic competence of future teachers.

6) Pedagogical support based on practicum supervision. In dual education, the effective organization of inclusive education is closely linked to the practicum supervision system. The practicum supervisor analyzes the student-teacher's practical activities in inclusive classrooms, provides methodological support, offers recommendations on selecting differentiated approaches, and organizes reflection processes. This strengthens the symmetric collaboration mechanism between higher education institutions, schools, and practicum supervisors.

In a dual education context, inclusive education and differentiated approaches contribute to the development of future teachers' professional competence based on the following criteria:

- Motivational-value criterion: awareness of the social significance of the teaching profession and responsibility for every child;
- Cognitive criterion: knowledge of the theoretical foundations of inclusive education and adaptation methodologies;
- Activity-practical criterion: ability to design differentiated tasks and conduct adapted lessons;
- Communicative criterion: effective interaction with students and parents, collaboration skills;
- Reflective criterion: ability to analyze one's own teaching activity and evaluate individual development dynamics.

These aspects further strengthen the didactic significance of developing inclusive competence in a dual education environment.

In the context of dual education, one of the key didactic directions required by the modern education system in developing the professional competence of future primary school teachers is the implementation of the STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics) approach and the methodology of teaching based on integrated subjects. The relevance of this approach lies in its ability to develop students' capacity to analyze real-life situations, solve problems, think logically and creatively, acquire knowledge through practical activity, and form skills and competencies in a comprehensive manner [2]. In this regard, the STEAM approach is directly aligned with the modern competency-based objectives of primary education.

The essence of the dual education model is based on the integration of theory and practice, requiring the development of professional competence of future teachers within a real pedagogical environment (school setting). In particular, within the "4+2" model, students

test the didactic approaches and methodological innovations learned at higher education institutions in real school practice and continuously improve them through reflective processes.

From this perspective, the STEAM and integrated subject approaches serve as important didactic resources for developing the methodological competence, innovative thinking, and activity-based professional competence of future primary school teachers.

The STEAM approach organizes education not as a system of separate subjects, but as a set of interconnected knowledge domains. In this model, learning materials are presented based on interdisciplinary connections and reinforced through students' activity-oriented experiences. In primary education, students' cognitive activity is enriched through experimentation, observation, design, modeling, construction, and creative problem-solving processes.

The didactic advantages of the STEAM approach include the following: ensuring the integration of knowledge, skills, and competencies; developing analytical and creative thinking in problem-based situations; enabling students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical activities; fostering systemic thinking through interdisciplinary integration; increasing student motivation and engagement in learning activities. Thus, the STEAM approach reveals didactic opportunities that correspond to the core objective of dual education—developing professional competence.

At the primary education level, students' worldview, thinking, and cognitive abilities are actively formed. At this stage, organizing knowledge based on interdisciplinary integration and orienting the learning process toward student-centered activities contributes to deeper understanding. The integrated subject approach fulfills the following didactic tasks: forming students' knowledge as a holistic system rather than fragmented units; solving practical tasks related to real-life situations; developing observation skills toward natural, social, and technological processes; enhancing logical and critical thinking; strengthening communicative competence through collaborative learning activities. Therefore, the integrated approach, as one of the modern directions in the development of primary education didactics, occupies an important place in the methodological training of future teachers.

The implementation of the STEAM approach in a dual education context is carried out through the integration of theoretical-methodological training at higher education institutions and practical activities in schools. This process can be organized based on the following mechanism (Table 1).

Table 1.

Mechanism for Implementing the STEAM Approach in Dual Education

No	Stage	Content (Scientific Description)	Main Activities	Outcome
1	Higher Education Stage (Theoretical-Methodological Training)	Mastering the theoretical and methodological foundations of the STEAM approach	STEAM theory; interdisciplinary integration; lesson design; technological mapping; project-based and problem-based learning	Development of competence in designing STEAM-based lessons

			methods	
2	School Stage (Practicum)	Application of theoretical knowledge in real pedagogical practice	Implementation of STEAM elements in lessons; interdisciplinary tasks; mini-projects; experiments and observations	Development of practical skills of the student- teacher
3	Practicum Supervision Stage (Analysis and Reflection)	Analysis and improvement of conducted lessons	Lesson observation; methodological analysis; identification of shortcomings; providing recommendations	Professional development ensured through reflective analysis

This integrated mechanism enables the development of the professional competence of future teachers through practical activities.

In a dual education context, the STEAM and integrated subject approaches contribute to the development of the following competencies of future primary school teachers (Table 2).

Table 2.

Professional Competencies Developed through the STEAM Approach

No	Type of Competence	Content (Scientific Description)	Manifestation in STEAM	Outcome
1	Cognitive Competence	Understanding and systematizing interdisciplinary knowledge	Integrating different subjects and linking concepts	Formation of comprehensive knowledge and analytical thinking
2	Activity-Practical Competence	Applying theoretical knowledge in practice	Designing and conducting STEAM lessons; creating mini-projects	Development of practical pedagogical mastery
3	Communicative Competence	Collaboration and communication skills	Group work; teamwork-based project activities	Development of effective communication and teamwork skills
4	Reflective Competence	Analyzing and evaluating one's own activity	Lesson analysis; identifying errors; drawing conclusions	Ensuring professional growth and self-development
5	Motivational-Value Competence	Interest in and value-based attitude toward professional activity	Aspiration for innovative approaches; interest in STEAM	Formation as a modern pedagogical professional

This confirms the necessity of recognizing the STEAM approach as a modern direction that expands the didactic possibilities of dual education.

In ensuring the methodological preparation of future teachers for the STEAM approach within a dual education context, the use of the following tools is essential: integrated lesson plans and technological maps; STEAM-based mini-projects and task banks; visual materials for experimental and observational activities; digital resources and interactive presentations; reflective journals and portfolios; criterion-based assessment rubrics. These tools strengthen the innovative methodological training of future primary school teachers.

Thus, the STEAM and integrated subject approaches in dual education represent a modern didactic direction for developing the professional competence of future primary school teachers. They enhance the integration of theory and practice, ensure the innovative nature of the educational process, and expand opportunities for developing methodological competence through practical activities. Therefore, integrating the STEAM approach into the content of integrated training sessions in dual education is an important didactic condition for preparing future primary school teachers as competitive, innovative, and modern pedagogical professionals.

As a result of the conducted analysis, it has been scientifically substantiated that in order to develop the professional competence of future primary school teachers in a dual education context, it is necessary to select forms, methods, and tools based on an integrated didactic system; organize them in a practice-oriented manner through the “4+2” mechanism and the collaboration model “higher education institution – school – practicum supervisor”; and implement competency-based assessment and monitoring on a criterion-based foundation. This approach strengthens the alignment between theoretical preparation and practical activity, reinforces methodological skills in real educational environments, and creates didactic conditions that contribute to improving the quality of primary education.

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